

ROLE OF EDUCATION IN EMPOWERMENT OF WOMEN IN PUSAD TAHISAL: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Education is a key factor for women's empowerment, prosperity, development, and well-being. Discrimination against women from pregnancy to death is well known. Inequality and vulnerability of women persist in all spheres and women are seen to be oppressed in many spheres of life, in such a situation there is a need to empower them in all spheres of life. To fight against sexism as a sense of social responsibility, women need to be empowered to play their role against this social order. Such power is developed through a process of empowerment, and empowerment can be developed through education. In this way, it will be possible to speed up the process of rural development through women's empowerment. The purpose of this research is to develop awareness about various empowerments among women and to study the effect of education on the overall empowerment of women in Pusad Tahsil of Yavatmal districts. A total of 400 women in the age group of 20-50 were selected for this research. The findings of this research show that educational qualification plays an important role in women's empowerment and if women's empowerment is to be achieved, it can only be achieved through education. For that, it is most important to raise the level of education of women in the society.

KEYWORDS: *Women empowerment, Education*

INTRODUCTION:

Many elements in society are deprived of their basic rights, but among these elements, they are not aware of their rights. If we note such elements of society, it can be seen that women rank high in this list. Women are the most important integral part of every society. Everyone is aware of this fact and yet no one is ready to accept this reality. Therefore, it is seen that the importance given to women in society in the past is continuously decreasing. This growing trend of belittling women such as giving them a secondary position in society and denying them their basic rights has led to the need for women's empowerment. Today we are enjoying the benefits of being a citizen of a free nation, but we need to think in the true sense of the word whether every citizen of our country is free, whether he is enjoying the joy of freedom. When it comes to our country, every Indian citizen has got some basic rights. The structure of our nation does not discriminate between men and women, but the destitute women

in our society have certain basic rights, which are conferred upon them by our constitution. In such a situation, there is a need to free these women from all constraints and empower them.

Women empowerment is not only limited to Indian society. If we consider the global aspect in this context, it is seen that women are treated equally in developed nations. If we look at history, we can see that women have always been given a secondary position in society, but the difference between men and women created by nature is natural. It is through education that we come to know this fact. When American women realized this, they protested the injustice that had been inflicted on them through mass protests, through which they demanded equal rights. To address this injustice, the United Nations Organization made a treaty called 'The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women', which further led to the establishment of the Commission on Women.

A review of this background shows that women's empowerment has become a topic of global discussion at present. Looking at all aspects of this discussion, we realize that education is the only tool for women's empowerment. Therefore, literacy should be promoted among women. In the latter period, the literacy rate among women is not as expected. As a nation, we dream of becoming a superpower. To become a superpower every element of our society/nation must contribute to the process of nation building. But we cannot expect to become a superpower if women, who are a major component of this society, are not literate. Therefore, we must know the importance of women's education, which will inspire the process of women's empowerment.

THE OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

1. To create awareness about various empowerment among women
2. To study the impact of education on the overall empowerment of women.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

The term empowerment has been overused and misused (Stromquist, 2002; Stuckey & Monkman, 2003). These are commonly used as synonyms for empowerment, inclusion, etc. The idea that education empowers women has gained a lot of popularity, although much remains to be learned about how education can empower women (Stromquist, 2002; DaCosta, 2008; Murphy-Graham, 2008). However, in the past few years, the goal of women's empowerment has often been seen as an effort by international organizations in the context of women's education.

Empowerment: Is there a multidimensional process of change from a state of disempowerment? It cannot be provided by a third party, as individuals are active in the process. It is shaped by context, and therefore indicators of empowerment must be sensitive to the context in which women live.

The root of the word empowerment is power. Therefore, the feminist approach to conceptualizing empowerment, which sees power as capability, while commenting on the feminist theory of power, shows that women's stress on power is not power as dominance, but power as capability, the capability of society as a whole, suggesting that women are more affected by relational experiences. Resources to further understand the power they can hold. The idea of power as capability is at the core of the concept of empowerment, where women's empowerment is seen as a process whereby women recognize their inherent worth, their inner strength, and need to begin efforts on equal terms to break down the patriarchy and promote social and economic development. Empowerment of women is not just for their happiness, but a crucial step towards establishing

gender equality. To some extent, gender equality manifests itself through the fair and equitable sharing of responsibilities between men and women. Gender is not synonymous with equality, and it does not mean that men and women are equal. Rather, it is a feature of social situations and relationships in which attitudes finality, and cooperation shape interactions and enable men and women to reach their full potential.

METHODOLOGY:

The survey method has been used in this research 200 women from Pusad taluka of Yavatmal districts in Western Vidarbha were selected for this research. For this, a random sampling method was used. A questionnaire was used to collect the facts regarding this research. A five-point scale was used in this research, with scores ranging from 1- strongly disagree to 5- strongly agree. Personal empowerment, educational empowerment, financial empowerment, social empowerment, mental empowerment, technical empowerment, and political empowerment were included in this questionnaire.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

In the study context of this research, inferential statistical techniques were used to analyze the facts.

Table no 1.1
Impact of Education on Women's Empowerment

Women empowerment	F-Ratio	Conclusion
Personal empowerment	3.45	H0 rejected
Educational Empowerment	2.10	H0 rejected
Financial Empowerment	6.21	H0 rejected
Social empowerment	5.71	H0 rejected
Mental empowerment	4.89	H0 rejected
Technological Empowerment	5.02	H0 rejected
Political empowerment	4.11	H0 rejected
Overall empowerment	7.25	H0 rejected

CONCLUSION:

The above study was conducted in the context of Pusad taluka in the Yavatmal district of West Vidarbha, the findings of this research show that there is a positive significant effect of women's educational qualification on total empowerment and other related empowerment factors. The educational, political, and psychological empowerment of women are important factors for their overall empowerment. Awareness of women's rights and needs is very important in the process of empowerment. The promotion of vocational education among women provides them with various employment opportunities and thereby increases their ability to secure their financial resources. During the fact collection, it was found that most of the respondents are educated and also have no awareness of empowerment. Education is the primary way to empower women. This has a positive impact on

the empowerment of women.

According to the present study, there is an urgent need for awareness programs to sensitize women in the context of modern development based on science and technology to accelerate the process of empowerment among rural women. It is the need of the hour to organize such women empowerment programs through the extension service department of schools and colleges. This will give away certain superstitions and attitudes among women. Rural women should be trained in various vocational courses like handloom and textile, poultry farming, fishery, dairy business, food and nutrition, fashion and designing, beauty parlour, etc. The women's reservation policy should be strictly followed in all respects. Like government appointments. And semi-government offices, admission to educational institutions, participation in politics, etc.

Gender barriers to women's empowerment persist, especially in rural areas. The research area covers more rural areas. Due to these socio-economic barriers in rural areas, women's potential is not fully utilized, thus pushing them further down the social hierarchy. In this, the majority of educated women feel that they are more capable than men. But women are neglected because of the ingrained feeling in men that they are less capable than men. Lack of education among women creates obstacles to their empowerment. After summarizing all the above aspects, it can be seen that there is a great need for change in the field of women's empowerment, and the pace of this positive change is less than expected. Education is indispensable to accelerate this process. In such a situation, if women's empowerment is to be done, it can only be done through education. Therefore, raising the level of education among women is of utmost importance.

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